

On the Dependence of the Point-Kinetic Response of the Neutron Noise on the Fraction of Delayed Neutrons

Demazière C*

¹Chalmers University of Technology, Department of Physics, Division of Subatomic, High Energy and Plasma Physics, SE-412 96 Gothenburg, Sweden

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803556

ABSTRACT

The possibility of localizing point-like perturbations in nuclear cores from the neutron noise measured at a few selected locations depends greatly on the deviation of the reactor response from point-kinetics. As the spatial dependence of the neutron noise in case of point-kinetic behaviour is given by the static flux, a point-kinetic dominated reactor response does not exhibit any information about the location of the perturbation. In this paper, the dependence of the magnitude of the point-kinetic component on the fraction of delayed neutrons is studied, both analytically and through numerical simulations. At plateau frequencies, it is demonstrated that the deviation from point-kinetics decreases with decreasing values of the fraction of delayed neutrons. For fuel typical of light water reactors, a decrease during fuel depletion due to Pu-239 build-up is noticed. The decrease is nevertheless not sufficient to jeopardize the possibility to infer from the measured neutron noise the position of the perturbation. For other systems, like fast reactors loading with MOX fuel or reactors based on the thorium-uranium fuel cycle, the decrease could be important.

Keywords: Reactor dynamics, neutron noise, point-kinetics, fraction of delayed neutrons

1. INTRODUCTION

The identification of potential perturbations existing in operating nuclear reactors from the neutron noise measured by in-core and ex-core neutron detectors has been proven to be an interesting core diagnostics technique [1-2]. Due to fission and scattering reactions, anomalies give rise to fluctuations in the neutron flux throughout the entire core. Local perturbations can thus be detected by distant neutron detectors. In the specific case of local perturbations, it is also of prime importance to determine their location. The shape of the spatial dependence of the induced neutron noise is the quantity of importance to recover the position of the perturbation.

In linear theory and in the frequency domain, the neutron noise in the energy group g induced at given location \mathbf{r} and angular frequency ω can be expressed as [1]:

$$\delta\phi_g(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \approx \phi_{g,0}(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\delta P(\omega)}{P_0} + P_0 \delta\psi_g(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \quad (1)$$

where $\phi_{g,0}(\mathbf{r})$ is the static neutron flux in position \mathbf{r} and in the energy group g , $\delta P(\omega)$ represents the fluctuations of the amplitude function and P_0 is its static value, and $\delta\psi_g(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ is the shape function in position \mathbf{r} and in the energy group g . The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (1) is referred to as the point-kinetic component of the neutron noise, whereas the second term is a space-dependent term representing the deviation from point-kinetics. Although both terms are space-dependent, the space-dependence of the point-kinetic term is given by the shape of the static flux and is thus independent of

*demaz@chalmers.se

the position of the actual local perturbation. Only the shape of the second term depends on the location of the perturbation. The possibility of recovering the location of the noise source entirely depends on how overwhelming the second term is in comparison to the first term. If the point-kinetic term dominates, the space-dependence of the induced neutron noise will essentially resemble the one of the static flux, thus making it impossible to recover the location of the noise source.

The relative fluctuations of the amplitude function can also be demonstrated to be given as [1]:

$$\frac{\delta P(\omega)}{P_0} = G_0(\omega) \delta \rho(\omega) \quad (2)$$

where $\delta \rho(\omega)$ is the Fourier-transform of the reactivity effect introduced by the noise source, and $G_0(\omega)$ is the zero-power reactor transfer function, given as:

$$G_0(\omega) = \frac{1}{\omega \left(\Lambda + \frac{\beta}{\omega + \lambda} \right)} \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3), β is the fraction of delayed neutrons, λ is the decay constant of the precursors of delayed neutrons (assuming one group of delayed neutrons) and Λ is the neutron mean generation time. For frequencies of interest in neutron noise diagnostics, one further has for the amplitude of the zero-power reactor transfer functions:

$$\|G_0(\omega)\| \approx \frac{1}{\beta} \quad (4)$$

Formally, the approximation above holds when $\omega \in [\lambda; \beta/\Lambda]$, referred to as the plateau region of the zero-power reactor transfer function. As Eqs. (1), (2) and (4) demonstrate, the dominance of the point-kinetic term is directly related to the fraction of delayed neutrons: the larger the fraction of delayed neutrons is, the smaller the point-kinetic term should be. On the other hand, a lower fraction of the fraction of delayed neutrons would lead to a more point-kinetic behavior of the system. As the fraction of delayed neutrons vary greatly between different fuel types and during fuel burnup, the purpose of this paper is to study the dependence of the dominance of the point-kinetic term on this fraction.

The paper is structured as follows. First, the system considered for this analysis is described and the modelling framework used for this investigation presented. Thereafter, the results based on the model are presented. The paper ends with some conclusions and outlook based on this analysis.

2. METHODOLOGY

A two-energy group model of the neutron noise induced by a local perturbation in a one-dimensional homogeneous system representative of a Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) was considered.

The macroscopic cross-sections and kinetic data required by the model were generated by OpenMC, version 0.15.2 [3]. A typical PWR fuel cell of uranium dioxide was used, for which the characteristics are given in Table I. Depletion calculations were performed until a burnup of 35 GWd/tHM using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library and depletion chains. 100 batches were used (out of which 10 were inactive), with 5000 particles per batch.

Table I. Characteristics of the PWR fuel cell.

Fuel pellet radius	0.39 cm
Cladding inner radius	0.40 cm
Cladding outer radius	0.46 cm
Fuel pin pitch	1.26 cm
Fuel pellet material	UO ₂ at 900 K

Cladding material	Zirconium at 600 K
Coolant material	Non-borated water at 578 K
Fuel enrichment	3%

The resulting variation of the infinite multiplication factor is represented in Fig. 1. During the fuel depletion, the concentration of U-235 decreases, whereas some plutonium is produced from U-238, as well as consumed. The variation of the concentration of those two species is given in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. Variation of the infinite multiplication factor with burnup of the modelled PWR fuel cell (the statistical uncertainties are too small to be represented).

Figure 2. Variation of the concentration of U-235 (left) and Pu-239 (right) with burnup of the modelled PWR fuel cell (the statistical uncertainties are too small to be represented).

As U-235 and Pu-239 have different fractions of delayed neutrons, the plutonium build-up results in a lowering of β from 694 pcm at a burnup of 0 GWd/tHM to, e.g., 518 pcm at a burnup of about 22 GWd/tHM. At about 35 GWd/tHM, one obtains 473 pcm.

Following the methodology presented in [1], the neutron noise at a location x induced by a point-like perturbation in x' and in the energy group g' is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} G_{g' \rightarrow 1}(x, x', \omega) \\ G_{g' \rightarrow 2}(x, x', \omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ c_\mu(\omega) \end{bmatrix} G_\mu(x, x', \omega) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ c_\nu(\omega) \end{bmatrix} G_\nu(x, x', \omega) \quad (5)$$

with

$$G_\mu(x, x', \omega) = \begin{cases} E_- \times \sin \{ \mu(\omega) \times [x + a] \}, & \text{for } x < x' \\ E_+ \times \sin \{ \mu(\omega) \times [x - a] \}, & \text{for } x > x' \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

and

$$G_\nu(x, x', \omega) = \begin{cases} F_- \times \sinh \{ \nu(\omega) \times [x + a] \}, & \text{for } x < x' \\ F_+ \times \sinh \{ \nu(\omega) \times [x - a] \}, & \text{for } x > x' \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In Eq. (5), $c_\mu(\omega)$ and $c_\nu(\omega)$ are two coupling coefficients. The expressions of those coefficients are not given here for the sake of brevity. We instead refer to [1]. In Eqs. (6) and (7), the coefficients E_\pm and F_\pm are obtained by expressing the continuity of the neutron noise in $x = x'$ and the discontinuity of the noise current in $x = x'$.

3. RESULTS

To appreciate the dominance of the point-kinetic component of the induced neutron noise, the induced neutron noise estimated using Eqs. (6) and (7) was decomposed into its point-kinetic component and the deviation from it. The point-kinetic component was estimated as [4]:

$$\delta\phi_g^{pk}(x, \omega) = \phi_{g,0}(x) \frac{\int_{-a}^a \left[\frac{1}{v_1} \phi_{1,0}^+(x) G_{g' \rightarrow 1}(x, x', \omega) + \frac{1}{v_2} \phi_{2,0}^+(x) G_{g' \rightarrow 2}(x, x', \omega) \right] dx'}{\int_{-a}^a \left[\frac{1}{v_1} \phi_{1,0}^+(x) \phi_{1,0}(x) + \frac{1}{v_2} \phi_{2,0}^+(x) \phi_{2,0}(x) \right] dx'} \quad (8)$$

resulting for the shape function or space-dependent term, based on Eq. (1), into:

$$P_0 \delta\psi_g(x, \omega) = G_{g' \rightarrow g}(x, x', \omega) - \delta\phi_g^{pk}(x, \omega) \quad (9)$$

In the following, the neutron noise induced by a point-like perturbation in the thermal group located in $x' = -30$ cm from the center of a reactor of size $2a = 300$ cm is represented in Figure 3 at a burnup of 0 GWd/tHM, and in Figure 4 at a burnup of 22 GWd/tHM.

Figure 3. Amplitude of the neutron noise induced by a thermal point-like perturbation located in $x' = -30$ cm at a frequency of 1 Hz and a burnup of 0 GWd/tHM. Fast neutron noise on the left and thermal neutron noise on the right.

Figure 4. Amplitude of the neutron noise induced by a thermal point-like perturbation located in $x' = -30$ cm at a frequency of 1 Hz and a burnup of 22 GWd/tHM. Fast neutron noise on the left and thermal neutron noise on the right.

The deviation from point-kinetics was also quantified using the following measure:

$$dev_{g' \rightarrow g}(x', \omega) = \frac{1}{2a} \int_{-a}^a \left\| \frac{G_{g' \rightarrow g}(x, x', \omega)}{\delta\phi_g^{pk}(x, \omega)} - 1 \right\| dx \quad (10)$$

As can be seen in Figures 3 and 4, the reactor behaves more in a point-kinetics kinetic manner, when the burnup increases, with the above measure in the thermal group decreasing from 0.30 at a burnup of 0 GWd/tHM to 0.24 at a burnup of 22 GWd/tHM. At a burnup of 35 GWd/tHM (results not displayed here for the sake of brevity – results very similar to the ones at a burnup of 22 GWd/tHM), this measure becomes 0.23. Keeping all parameters equal to the ones at a burnup of 0 GWd/tHM but only changing the fraction of delayed neutrons to the one of the burnup of 22 GWd/tHM gives the same result. This means that the fact that the neutron noise deviates less at a burnup of 22 GWd/tHM is mostly driven by the reduction of the fraction of delayed neutrons. Even if not drastic, the reduction of the deviation from point-kinetics with burnup may be of concern for very long fuel cycles (such as 24-month cycles).

Although determining a threshold below which the dominance of the point-kinetic component becomes too severe to detect the position of perturbations is difficult, one notices that the variation due to burnup in the LWR case above seems negligible. If in-core instrumentation is sufficient to recover the spatial dependence of the noise, one might thus expect to be able to retrieve the location of the perturbation from the spatial dependence of the induced neutron noise, despite the decrease of the fraction of delayed neutrons with burnup.

In order to get a more comprehensive view on the dependence of the reactor response on the fraction of delayed neutrons, some additional cases were investigated. Keeping the material data to the ones of the LWR fuel cell considered above, both the fraction of delayed neutrons and the angular frequency of the perturbation were varied. The measure defined in Eq. (10) corresponding to frequencies of 0.01, 0.1, 1.0, and 10.0 Hz and to fractions of delayed neutrons of 694, 518, 473, 352, and 220 pcm is given in Table II. Concerning the fractions of delayed neutrons, the first three values correspond to the considered PWR fuel cell at burnups of 0 GWd/tHM, 22 GWd/tHM and 35 GWd/tHM, respectively, whereas the next to last value could be representatives of, e.g., a fast reactor loaded with MOX fuel [5]. The last value corresponds to pure Pu-239 [6]. U-233 has a similar fraction of delayed neutrons of 260 pcm [6]. Furthermore, for each of the fractions of delayed neutrons, the lower and upper bounds (in Hz) of the plateau region, i.e., $\lambda/(2\pi)$ and $\beta/(2\pi\Lambda)$, respectively, are given in Table III. Whereas the lower bound is independent of the fraction of delayed neutrons, the upper bound decreases for decreasing fractions of delayed neutrons. As demonstrated in Table III, frequencies of 0.1 and 1.0 Hz are well within the plateau region for all fractions of delayed neutrons. Frequencies of 0.01 Hz are slightly outside of the plateau region for all fractions of delayed neutrons. Frequencies of 10.0 Hz are close to the upper bound of the plateau region only for very low values of the fraction of delayed neutrons (i.e., when $\beta = 220$ pcm).

Table II. Variation of $dev_{2 \rightarrow 2}(x' = -30 \text{ cm}, \omega = 2\pi f)$ at different frequencies f and for different fractions of delayed neutrons β .

	$\beta = 694 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 518 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 473 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 352 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 220 \text{ pcm}$
$f = 0.01 \text{ Hz}$	0.225	0.177	0.163	0.127	0.083
$f = 0.1 \text{ Hz}$	0.297	0.242	0.227	0.183	0.127
$f = 1.0 \text{ Hz}$	0.297	0.243	0.228	0.184	0.128
$f = 10.0 \text{ Hz}$	0.308	0.258	0.245	0.207	0.165

Table III. Variation of the frequency bounds of the plateau region for different fractions of delayed neutrons β .

	$\beta = 694 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 518 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 473 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 352 \text{ pcm}$	$\beta = 220 \text{ pcm}$
Lower bound $\lambda/(2\pi)$ [Hz]	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.015
Upper bound $\beta/(2\pi\Lambda)$ [Hz]	39.058	29.153	26.620	19.810	12.382

As Table II demonstrates, the deviation from point-kinetics decreases for lower frequencies. This behaviour was expected, as it is known from the existing literature that the reactor response is more

point-kinetics at low frequencies [1]. In addition to this frequency dependence, a clear dependence on the fraction of delayed neutrons also exists, with a lower fraction of delayed neutrons leading to a more pronounced point-kinetic behaviour. As also demonstrated in Table III, the deviation from point-kinetics is almost independent of the frequencies in the plateau region. As in the plateau region, the amplitude of the zero-power reactor transfer function given by Eq. (4) only depends on the fraction of delayed neutrons, only a dependence on the fraction of delayed neutrons thus remains.

As an illustration, the induced neutron noise at 1.0 Hz and for a fraction of delayed neutrons of 220 pcm is given in Figure 5. Compared to Figure 3, the dominance of the point-kinetic behaviour for a reduced fraction of delayed neutrons is significant, which makes it more challenging to localize point-like perturbations.

Figure 5. Amplitude of the neutron noise induced by a thermal point-like perturbation located in $x' = -30$ cm at a frequency of 1.0 Hz and a burnup of 0 GWd/tHM. The fraction of delayed neutrons was artificially modified to be 220 pcm. Fast neutron noise on the left and thermal neutron noise on the right.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, the dependence of the neutron noise on the fraction of delayed neutrons was investigated. It was demonstrated, both theoretically and numerically, that the fraction of delayed neutrons plays a significant role in the possible deviation from point-kinetics of the reactor response. At plateau frequencies of the zero-power reactor transfer function, the amplitude of the transfer function is inversely proportional to the fraction of delayed neutrons. A lower fraction of delayed neutrons thus leads to a larger point-kinetic component of the reactor response. For diagnostics tasks aimed at recovering the location of a possible localized noise source, a larger point-kinetic component makes it more difficult to detect the location of the noise source, as this component has the same space-dependence as the one of the static flux and is thus independent of the location of the perturbation. The numerical simulations representative of PWR conditions nevertheless reveal that the increase of the point-kinetic component related to Pu-239 build-up during fuel depletion remains small, and is thus not jeopardizing the possibility to recover the location of noise sources. On the other hand, it was also demonstrated that the variations of the macroscopic cross-sections due to fuel depletion had a negligible impact on the deviation from point-kinetics, whereas artificially modifying the fraction of delayed neutrons had a major impact on the deviation of the reactor response from point-kinetics.

Extrapolating those findings to systems fueled with more Pu-239 (like in a fast reactor) or using the thorium-uranium fuel cycle (leading to U-233), the increase of the point-kinetic component is expected to be significant. For fast reactor systems, the possibility to detect the location of a noise source will furthermore be complicated by a larger mean free path for fast neutrons, as compared to thermal neutrons. As already seen in, e.g., [5], the deviation from point-kinetics might be very small, as a result of both a larger mean free path and a smaller fraction of delayed neutrons. Further investigations are necessary to quantify those effects.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Pázsit and C. Demazière. *Noise techniques in nuclear systems*. Chapter in the *Handbook of Nuclear Engineering*, by D. Cacuci (Ed.), ISBN 978-0-387-98150-5, Springer, New York, USA, Vol. 3 (2010). URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-98149-9>
- [2] C. Demazière. Editorial (to the special issue on “Neutron noise-based core diagnostics and monitoring of nuclear reactors – Outcomes of the Horizon 2020 CORTEX project”). *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **212**, 110938 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2024.110938>
- [3] P. K. Romano, N. E. Horelik, B. R. Herman, A. G. Nelson, B. Forget, and K. Smith. “OpenMC: A State-of-the-Art Monte Carlo Code for Research and Development”. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **82**, 90–97 (2015). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2014.07.048>
- [4] C. Demazière, V. Dykin and K. Jareteg. “Development of a point-kinetic verification scheme for nuclear reactor applications”. *Journal of Computational Physics*, **339**, 396-411 (2017). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2017.03.020>
- [5] H. Hansen and T. Hansson. “On the feasibility of neutron noise diagnostics in fast Gen-IV reactors”. Master of Science thesis. Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden (2025). URL <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12380/309507>
- [6] T. W. Kerlin and B. R. Upadhyaya. *Dynamics and control of nuclear reactors*. Academic Press/Elsevier (2019). In: URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815261-4.00003-2>